

Partial molar volumes and viscosities of some amino acids in aqueous electrolyte and non-electrolyte solutions

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Apparent molar volumes and viscosities of glycine, DL- α -alanine and L-leucine in water and in 1.0 m (mol kg⁻¹) aqueous solutions of each of potassium chloride, barium chloride, glucose and sucrose have been determined from density and efflux time measurements, using vibrating-tube digital densimeter and Ubbelohde viscometer, respectively at 298.15 K. Volume data were utilised to calculate partial molar volumes of transfer at infinite dilution ($v_{2,tr}^0$) from water to mixed aqueous solutions and B -coefficients were calculated from viscosity data using Jones-Dole equation. Positive $v_{2,tr}^0$ values have been rationalized using cosphere overlap model in terms of solute-cosolute interactions. Transfer B -coefficients of the amino acids studied are positive in case of glucose and sucrose whereas these are negative in case of electrolytes (KCl, BaCl₂) which have been explained in terms of changes in solvent structure. Contributions of the side chain to $v_{2,tr}^0$ and to B -coefficient values have also been discussed.

Thermodynamic properties of aqueous solutions of amino acids, small peptides and their derivatives which mimic some of the structural features of proteins, assist in understanding of the conformational stability and folding behaviour of globular proteins¹⁻⁵. The conformational transitions of biopolymers are extremely sensitive to subtle changes in the solvent medium⁶⁻⁹. Currently there exists considerable interest in the use of mixed aqueous solutions to control various factors like stability and reactivity of the proteins.

Salt solutions have been known to produce remarkable effects on the conformational properties of proteins like denaturation, dissociation into subunits and activity of enzymes^{6,7}. On the other hand it is well known that sugars and polyols help in stabilizing the native conformation of globular proteins^{9,10}. Although some trends correlating the stabilizing potency of sugars and polyols with the number and configuration of the hydroxyl groups have been noted, proteins do not respond equally to a given compound¹⁰. In spite of a large number of studies on the effect of salts and sugars or polyols on proteins and model compounds, the mechanism of denaturation/dissociation/stabilization by these additives is not clearly understood. Literature survey reveals few reports on the transport properties of the amino acids in mixed aqueous medium^{7,11}. Therefore, in continuation of our work^{5,8}, we report here the partial molar volumes (v_2^0) and B -coefficients of glycine, DL- α -alanine and L-leucine in aqueous and in mixed 1.0 m (mol kg⁻¹) each of

aqueous solutions of electrolytes (potassium chloride, barium chloride) and non-electrolytes (glucose and sucrose) at 298.15 K. Transfer parameters obtained from these results have been discussed in terms of solute-cosolute interactions using cosphere overlap model. Side chain contributions have also been discussed.

Results and discussion

Apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) of amino acids in aqueous (1.0 m each) solutions of potassium chloride and barium chloride were determined from the density measurements using the following relation,

$$\phi_v = M_2/d[1000(d - d_0)/mdd_0] \quad (1)$$

where M_2 is the molecular mass of the solute, m is the molarity of the solution and, d and d_0 are the densities of solution and solvent, respectively. The values of d and ϕ_v as a function of molarity in mixed aqueous solutions at 298.15 K are given in Table 1. As ϕ_v values have linear dependence on m over the concentration range studied, therefore the apparent molar volumes at infinite dilution ($\phi_v^0 = v_2^0$) have been calculated by linear regression analysis of the data as follows

$$\phi_v^0 = v_2^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where S_v is the slope.

Partial molar volumes of transfer ($v_{2,tr}^0$) from water to

Table 1. Density (d) and apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) and relative viscosities (η_r) of some amino acids in aqueous solutions of potassium chloride and barium chloride at 298.15 K

m mol kg ⁻¹	d g cm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹	η_r
In 1.0 m aqueous potassium chloride solution :			
Glycine			
0.07640	1.04378	44.76	1.0093
0.15264	1.04597	44.82	1.0184
0.16873	1.04644	44.83	1.0200
0.20471	1.04704	44.85	1.0237
0.24843	1.04876	44.87	1.0290
0.27325	1.04946	44.90	1.0316
0.34430	1.05148	44.93	1.0392
DL- α -Alanine			
0.01405	1.04188	62.15	1.0031
0.15069	1.04537	62.18	1.0335
0.17626	1.04593	62.23	1.0389
0.19405	1.04638	62.20	1.0427
0.22273	1.04708	62.21	1.0480
0.27325	1.04831	62.24	1.0585
0.41346	1.05168	62.28	1.0873
L-Leucine			
0.02474	1.04200	108.16	1.0103
0.03660	1.04223	108.20	1.0153
0.05021	1.04249	108.22	1.0230
0.06033	1.04268	108.26	1.0252
0.06575	1.04278	108.29	1.0274
0.08211	1.04308	108.34	1.0343
In 1.0 m aqueous barium chloride solutions :			
Glycine			
0.02737	1.19815	49.38	1.0034
0.11573	1.19980	49.44	1.0142
0.15559	1.20054	49.48	1.0188
0.24207	1.20211	49.52	1.0290
0.29407	1.20305	49.56	1.0347
0.31074	1.20516	49.58	1.0363
0.45483	1.20587	49.65	1.0527
DL- α -Alanine			
0.03382	1.19798	67.21	1.0077
0.12780	1.19892	67.25	1.0292
0.22003	1.19982	67.31	1.0499
0.25034	1.20013	67.29	1.0549
0.27345	1.20034	67.33	1.0615
0.30980	1.20068	67.55	1.0693
0.35245	1.20106	67.40	1.0778
L-Leucine			
0.01872	1.19733	108.42	1.0080

Table-1 (contd.)

0.02767	1.19734	108.47	1.0118
0.03988	1.19735	108.60	1.0171
0.06275	1.19738	108.63	1.0269
0.08379	1.19739	108.74	1.0359

mixed aqueous solutions at infinite dilution were estimated as follows :

$$v_{2,tr}^0 = v_2^0 \text{ (in mixed aqueous solutions)} - v_2^0 \text{ (in water)}$$

v_2^0 and $v_{2,tr}^0$ values along with standard deviations are presented in Table 2.

The viscosity (η) values were used to determine relative viscosities (η_r) using the relation ($\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$, where η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent) and the values are summarized in Tables 1, 3 and 4. Density data for amino acids in water and in aqueous sugar solutions reported in literature have been utilized^{5,8}. η_r values were fitted by the method of least squares to the Jones-Dole equation of the following form to estimate B -coefficients

$$\eta_r = 1 + Bc \tag{3}$$

where c is the molarity (calculated from molality). B -coefficients for various amino acids are given in Tables 5 and 6. The transfer B -coefficients (ΔB) of the amino acids from water to mixed aqueous solutions calculated similarly as $v_{2,tr}^0$ values, are given in Table 7. $v_{2,tr}^0$ and B -coefficient values of R groups (side chain group) ($v_{2,tr}^0(R)$ and $\Delta B(R)$) were also obtained by subtracting the values of glycine from the corresponding amino acids and the values are also given in Table 7.

v_2^0 values of the studied amino acids are higher in 1.0 m aqueous potassium chloride and barium chloride solutions than the corresponding values in water which exhibit positive $v_{2,tr}^0$ (Table 2). $v_{2,tr}^0$ values for glycine and DL- α -alanine (1.57 and 1.43 cm³ mol⁻¹, respectively) from water to 1.0 m potassium chloride solution at 298.15 K are comparable with the corresponding reported^{12,13} values (1.3 and 1.4 cm³ mol⁻¹) from water to 0.8 m aqueous potassium chloride solution. No data are available in barium chloride solution. These results can be explained using the cosphere overlap model as developed by Gurney¹⁴. Properties of water molecules in the hydration cospheres depend on the nature of solute species and the overlap of cospheres is accompanied by changes in thermodynamic parameters¹⁵. The various interactions occurring in these systems can be classified as (i) ionic-ionic group interactions occurring between ions of the electrolytes and zwitterionic centres of the amino acids and (ii) ionic-hydrophobic interactions between ions of electrolytes and non-polar parts of the amino acids. Ac-

$$v_{2}^{0} = v_{v,w} + v_{\text{void}} - v_{\text{shrinkage}} \quad (4)$$

where $v_{v,w}$ is the van der Waals volume, v_{void} is the volume associated with the voids or empty spaces there in and $v_{\text{shrinkage}}$ is the shrinkage in volume due to the interaction of solute with solvent. If it is assumed³ that $v_{v,w}$ and v_{void} remain of the same magnitude in water and mixed aqueous solutions, the positive volumes of transfer for the amino acids can be explained to result from the decrease in $v_{\text{shrinkage}}$ in the presence of electrolyte molecules in aqueous solutions. This may be due to the stronger interactions occurring between charged centres of amino acids and the ions of the electrolytes. Due to overlap of hydration cospheres of these charged species it is obvious that the electrostriction of the neighbouring water molecules due to these will be reduced in the presence of electrolytes. This will lead to a reduction in the shrinkage volume. Furthermore, due to these interactions the structure-breaking tendencies of these elec-

trolytes will also be reduced, which will also lead to a positive volume of transfer.

The positive $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ values decrease from glycine to L-leucine with the exception of slight increase for alanine in case of barium chloride i.e. with the increase in size of the non-polar part of the amino acids the $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ values decrease. This observation indicates the reduction in ion-ion interactions with the simultaneous increase in the ion-hydrophobic interactions. The higher $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ values in case of barium chloride than in potassium chloride may be attributed to the stronger interactions of barium chloride ions with the NH_3^+ and COO^- centres of amino acids. Further, the comparison of $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ values with the literature values (Table 2) shows that the values in the case of potassium chloride and barium chloride come out to be higher as compared to sodium chloride and calcium chloride, respectively, except in case L-leucine where the reverse is true. These results may be attributed to the effective overlap of charged centres of amino acids with K^+ and Ba^{2+} ions than with Na^+ and Ca^{2+} ions in case of glycine and DL- α -alanine, whereas in case of L-leucine the contribution from ion-hydrophobic interactions is more due to overlapping of large size hydration cospheres of ions of electrolytes and non-polar side chain of L-leucine which is responsible for smaller values of $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$, $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0(\text{R})$ values (Table 7) indicate that contributions of R groups to $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ are very small and mostly negative which indicate that the positive $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ values (Table 2) are the resultant of stronger interactions involving the charge centres of amino acids. Similar conclusion have been drawn by Bhat and Ahluwalia³ from their $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0$ and $C_{p,2,\text{tr}}^0$ studies.

Table 4. Relative viscosities of some amino acids in aqueous solutions of 1.0 m each glucose and sucrose at 298.15 K

	m mol kg ⁻¹	η_r	m mol kg ⁻¹	η_r
Glycine				
In 1.0 m aqueous glucose solution	0.09564	1.0102	0.11015	1.0123
	0.19136	1.0246	0.22783	1.0297
	0.25573	1.0354	0.51683	1.0795
	0.53912	1.0842		
DL- α -Alanine				
	0.07523	1.0192	0.15046	1.0383
	0.17811	1.0454	0.20677	1.0525
	0.22520	1.0567	0.25727	1.0643
	0.27427	1.0680		
L-Leucine				
	0.01390	1.0082	0.03274	1.0165
	0.04517	1.0222	0.05898	1.0287
	0.06739	1.0329	0.08376	1.0438
Glycine				
In 1.0 m aqueous sucrose solution	0.15216	1.0240	0.19247	1.0302
	0.21358	1.0333	0.24533	1.0380
	0.29275	1.0450	0.33216	1.0508
DL- α -Alanine				
	0.06573	1.0180	0.13475	1.0369
	0.18345	1.0500	0.21459	1.0583
	0.23425	1.0637	0.26325	1.0713
L-Leucine				
	0.03245	1.0202	0.04385	1.0273
	0.06575	1.0410	0.07354	1.0458
	0.08395	1.0523	0.09436	1.0590

Table 5. B-coefficients of amino acids in water at different temperatures

T/K	Glycine	DL- α -Alanine	L-Leucine
298.15	0.134	0.241	0.453
	0.135 ^a	0.247 ^a	
	0.142 ^b		
308.15	0.142	0.255	
	0.139 ^c	0.250 ^c	
	0.144 ^d		
318.15	0.151	0.257	
	0.152 ^e		

^aRef. 21. ^bRef. 22. ^cRef. 23. ^dRef. 24. ^eRef. 16.

B-coefficients for the amino acids in water are in good agreement with the literature values¹⁸⁻²² (Table 5). The B-coefficients of glycine, DL- α -alanine and L-leucine are positive and increase in magnitude from glycine to L-leucine and also increase with temperature. The relative magnitude of B-coefficients gives indication about the structure of the

solution. As the size and shape of solute molecules are important in determining the B -coefficients and size and shape of amino acid molecules are mainly determined by the side chain, the observed weaker structure breaking effect of L-leucine may be attributed to the shielding effect of large non-polar group on the hydration cosphere of charged centres of amino acids.

Positive value of dB/dT is characteristic of structure breaking and negative value of structure-making solute²³. Present positive dB/dT values 0.00085 and 0.00080 for glycine and DL- α -alanine respectively suggest that these solutes are structure-breakers and the comparison of dB/dT values indicates that DL- α -alanine is weaker structure breaker solute between the two.

Table 6. B -coefficients of amino acids in aqueous solutions of various cosolutes at 298.15

Cosolutes	B -coefficients $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$		
	Glycine	DL- α -Alanine	L-Leucine
Glucose (1.0 m)	0.139	0.247	0.479
Sucrose (1.0 m)	0.142	0.250	0.570
Potassium chloride (1.0 m)	0.112	0.211	0.408
Barium chloride (1.0 m)	0.099	0.190	0.361

B -coefficients of glycine, DL- α -alanine and L-leucine (Table 6) are less in 1.0 m aqueous potassium chloride and barium chloride solutions than the corresponding values in water, which result in negative ΔB values. These transfer B -coefficients decrease in the following order : glycine > DL- α -alanine > L-leucine. Negative ΔB values indicate that the amino acids are in less structural environment in the presence of potassium chloride and barium chloride which may be due to structure breaking characteristics of these electrolytes. In terms of solute-cosolute interactions the ΔB may be resulting from the interactions of electrolytes and R groups or charged centres of amino acids. From $\Delta B(R)$ values (Table

7), it can again be seen that contributions of R groups to ΔB values is much less than 50% which shows that main contribution to ΔB values comes from the interactions between charged centres of amino acids and salt ions rather than from interactions between R groups of amino acids and salt ions. Similar observations have been reported from the studies of amino acids in the presence of guanidine hydrochloride¹⁹.

The decrease in ΔB values for amino acids in aqueous barium chloride solutions is slightly more as compared to that in aqueous potassium chloride solution. While comparing the extent of decrease in B -coefficient of glycine, DL- α -alanine and L-leucine, it may be observed that decrease in B -coefficient is more prominent in case of L-leucine as compared to DL- α -alanine and glycine because L-leucine is comparatively weaker structure breaker than glycine and DL- α -alanine. Therefore, the effect of these electrolytes will be more prominent in case of L-leucine as compared to glycine and DL- α -alanine. ΔB values are positive for amino acids in aqueous glucose and sucrose solutions and increase in the following order : glycine < DL- α -alanine < L-leucine. This trend can again be explained by considering both the modification in the solvent medium caused by the cosolute molecules and size and shape of solute molecules. Positive ΔB values indicate that these amino acids are in more structured environment in the presence of glucose and sucrose. Various thermodynamic properties²⁴ of aqueous solutions of sugars have shown that these compounds act as structure promoters. Thus the increase in structure of the solution is responsible for the high viscosity value of the amino acids in presence of these cosolutes. Positive ΔB values may be attributed to the interactions of sugar molecules with charged centres and/or R groups of amino acid molecules and in order to see the contributions of these interactions separately $\Delta B(R)$ values have been calculated (Table 7). Value of $\Delta B(R)$ in case of L-leucine comes out to be higher as compared to

Table 7. ΔB , $\Delta B(R)$ and $v_{2,\text{tr}}^0(R)$ values for amino acids in the presence of various cosolutes at 298.15 K

Amino Acid	ΔB	$\Delta B(R)$	ΔB	$\Delta B(R)$	ΔB	$\Delta B(R)$	ΔB	$\Delta B(R)$
	Glucose	Glucose	Sucrose	Sucrose	Potassium chloride	Potassium chloride	Barium chloride	Barium chloride
Glycine	0.005		0.008		-0.022		-0.350	
DL- α -Alanine	0.006	0.001	0.009	0.001	-0.030	-0.008	-0.051	-0.016
L-Leucine	0.026	0.021	0.117	0.111	-0.045	-0.021	-0.092	-0.055
				$v_{2,\text{tr}}^0(R)$				
				$\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$				
Glycine								
DL- α -Alanine		-0.58		-0.94		-0.14		-0.21
L-Leucine		-0.88		-1.02		-1.27		-5.65

that is DL- α -alanine. It is again due to greater structure breaking behaviour of DL- α -alanine as compared to L-leucine. When $\Delta B(R)$ values (Table 7) are compared with ΔB values, it can be seen that the contribution of R groups to the increase in B -coefficients is much less than 50% in case of DL- α -alanine which shows that the main contribution to ΔB values comes from the interactions between charged centres of DL- α -alanine and sugars. However in case of leucine $\Delta B(R)$ values are even more than 80% of ΔB which suggest that the shielding effect of non-polar group in L-leucine is quite prominent. These findings are in line with the volume results.

Experimental

Glycine (G-7126), DL- α -alanine (A-7126) and L-leucine (L-8000) from Sigma Chem. Co., glucose (A.R.), sucrose (A.R.), potassium chloride (A.R.) and barium chloride (A.R.) from Qualigens were used without further purification, however before use, these were dried and kept over P_2O_5 in vacuum desiccator. Water used for solutions was deionized, doubly glass-distilled and degassed by boiling. All solutions were made on weight basis. The densities of the solutions were measured using vibrating-tube digital densimeter (Model DMA 60/602, Anton Paar, Austria). The details of its principle and working have been described elsewhere^{25,26}. The temperature of the densimeter cell was controlled using temperature bath (Birkerod/Denmark) having stability within ± 0.01 K. The densimeter was calibrated using dry air and water and its working was checked by determining densities of sodium chloride solution, which agree very well with the literature values.

The viscosities of the solutions were determined using Ubbelohde viscometer by placing it in water thermostat having thermal stability better than ± 0.01 K. Efflux time was measured with an accuracy of 0.1 s and the average of at least four readings was taken. The viscometer was calibrated by determining efflux times (t) of water between 298.15 to 328.15 K using literature values²⁷ of viscosities (η) and densities (d), for water and the data were fitted to the equation :

$$\eta = d(a - bt) \quad (5)$$

where a and b are viscometer constants. The reproducibility of the viscosity measurements was better than ± 0.001 mPa S.

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